

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON STORAGE TIME OF SOLUTION A*

[ADA]=0.0056 M, [Ce^{III}]=0.005 M, [KBrO₃]=0.03 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5 M

Storage time (hrs)	20°						26°						
	t_{in}		t		t_1		t_{in}		t		t_1		A mV
	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	min	s	
2	4'	45"	2'	50"	70'		3'	25"	2'	20"	53'		90
4	21'		1'		43'								40
8	18'		2'	10"	155'		15'	50"	1'	30"	110'		60
∞	21'		10'		120'		18'	30"	8'		130'		-300

0.1M Ce^{VI} sulphate (1.1 ml) were mixed and stored in a thermostat at a required temperature for the desired length of time (*viz.* 2, 4, 8 h or infinite time). Each solution A* was used to study the oscillatory characteristics along with 0.03 M potassium bromate solution (10 ml). The e.m.f. values were measured every 5 s with the help of a digital potentiometer.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the variation of time of initiation (t_{in}), time period (t) and life-time (t_1) of oscillations, when the solution A* containing acetone dicarboxylic acid was stored at different lengths of time at the temperatures 20±0.05° and 26±0.05°.

The time of initiation of oscillations increased very sharply as the components of solution A* were allowed to stand for successively more time period at any temperature. This delay in the onset of oscillations may be due to the fact that the system requires time to accumulate sufficient amount of brominated organic species which can trigger off the oscillations. Acetone dicarboxylic acid decomposes⁷ very easily on standing to acetone, a non-promoter of oscillations. The longer the time the solution A* was stored the lesser would be the amount of compound effective in oscillation. Acetone is known to get brominated easily⁸ and thus consumes the major portions of reacting bromine species like Br⁻, BrO₃⁻ and HBrO₂, thereby leaving very little of them for bromination of acetone dicarboxylic acid and other compounds (which might have been formed) that help to promote the oscillations. This also increases the time period of oscillations gradually, as oscillations did exist in the cases of a weak old solutions A* (tagged infinite time) but were least frequent (Table 1).

The amplitude of oscillations showd a general decreasing trend with the increase in storage time, so much so that for the solutions stored infinitely, there was sharp drop in potential of the systems giving rise to sort of inverted peaks. The oscillations are well defined and were most prominent in case of 2 h storing of solution A* as the amount of acetone dicarboxylic acid was maximum, but this amount gradually decreased with the length of storing.

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Isothermal Diffusion Coefficient of Tetra-alkylammonium Salts in Aqueous Solutions

S. K. SANYAL* and (Miss) S. BANDYOPADHYAY

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

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THE present communication reports the isothermal diffusion coefficients (D) of tetraethylammonium chloride and bromide, as well as those of tetra-n-butylammonium bromide and nitrate in aqueous solutions at 35 and 40°. A Stokes' type of diaphragm diffusion cell^{1,2} has been used for the purpose with the following working relation²,

$$D = \frac{1}{\beta t} \ln \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_3 - C_4} \quad (1)$$

where, D is the (double average) diaphragm cell integral diffusion coefficient, β is the cell constant, and $(C_1 - C_2)$ and $(C_3 - C_4)$ are the initial and final (*i.e.*, after time t) concentration differences between the cell compartments.

In order to check the reliability of the present results in terms of the Stokes-Einstein equation for temperature dependence of D , the viscosity coefficients (η) of the solutions used have been measured at 35 and 40° by using a Ubbelohde viscometer³.

Experimental

Diffusion experiments: The diaphragm cell used for measuring diffusion coefficient was similar to

TABLE 1—DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS OF TETRAALKYLAMMONIUM SALTS

Salt	Concn. M	$(C_1 - C_2)$ at 35° $\times 10^8 M$	$(C_3 - C_4)$ at 35° $\times 10^8 M$	$(C_1 - C_3)$ at 40° $\times 10^8 M$	$(C_2 - C_4)$ at 40° $\times 10^8 M$	$D (\times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$ at				$\frac{D_1}{D_2}$	$\frac{\eta_2 T_1}{\eta_1 T_2}$
						35° (D_1)	40° (D_2)	35° (η_1)	40° (η_2)		
Tetraethyl- ammonium chloride	0.05	47.32 ± 0.552	41.47 ± 0.377	48.59 ± 1.170	41.63 ± 0.665	1.081 ± 0.0254	1.250 ± 0.2093	0.733 ± 0.0025	0.669 ± 0.0007	0.8644	0.8933
Tetraethyl- ammonium bromide	0.05	46.41 ± 1.707	41.05 ± 1.699	47.25 ± 1.333	40.90 ± 1.920	1.060 ± 0.0495	1.231 ± 0.1796	0.759 ± 0.0027	0.693 ± 0.0030	0.8613	0.8977
Tetra-n-butyl- ammonium nitrate	0.05	42.57 ± 2.373	39.50 ± 1.961	46.18 ± 3.351	41.97 ± 2.559	0.661 ± 0.0415	0.872 ± 0.0805	0.773 ± 0.0046	0.695 ± 0.0000	0.7573	0.8826
Tetra-n-butyl- ammonium bromide	0.05	42.73 ± 0.175	41.55 ± 2.121	49.03 ± 0.736	44.93 ± 0.736	0.5667 ± 0.0189	0.687 ± 0.0386	0.915 ± 0.0045	0.787 ± 0.0045	0.8247	0.8488

The mean cell constant⁴ ($=0.083 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was checked once more in the present work.

Viscosity (η) of water at 25° = 0.8903, 35° = 0.7194, 40° = 0.6529 c.p. (Ref. 8). $D_{25^\circ} (10^5)$ for 0.05 M KCl = 1.893 $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Ref. 6).

the one used by Stokes^{1,2}. It was made of a glass tubing (i.d. 2.3 cm) divided into two compartments by pyrex G-4 sintered glass disc. The volumes of the upper and lower compartments were 45.8 and 48.0 ml, respectively. The solutions in these compartments were stirred by means of a magnetic stirring arrangement⁴. The diffusion cell was mounted in an air-thermostat, maintained within $\pm 0.05^\circ$ of the temperature of study. The air-thermostat consisted of a wooden box, having an electric bulb (100 W), an electric fan (REMI) situated inside the thermostat, and an electrical contact thermometer inserted through a hole into the thermostat. The box was insulated with polystyrene foam on the inside of the front wall, the wall having a door that can be opened whenever necessary. The solution-filled methodology⁵ was followed in the present case in order to avoid the long pre-diffusion period required for establishing the steady state in the diaphragm. While mounting the diffusion cell in the appropriate position inside the thermostat, due care was taken to keep the diaphragm within an inclination of 1° of the horizontal position.

The salts used were of AnalaR or G.R. grade; or else the purest grade available, which was further purified by crystallisation (twice) from water. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water of specific conductance $< 3 \mu \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The cell constant (*vide* equation 1) was checked against the earlier determination⁴ by way of conducting the calibration experiment at 25° using KCl solution (0.05 M) which was allowed to diffuse into pure water in the bottom compartment. The relevant D used was the literature value⁶ of D_{KCl} (0.05 M) at 25°. Actual diffusion runs with the present solutes were performed by following the same technique as that for the calibration experiment. On completion of the requisite diffusion period ($\sim 48 \text{ h}$), solutions from both the compartments were withdrawn and their concentrations measured by conductometric titration against standard AgNO_3 solution. For tetra-n-butylammonium nitrate, the

nitrate concentration was estimated spectrophotometrically by phenol disulphonic acid method at 420 nm⁷.

Viscosity measurements: The viscosity coefficients of the solutions were measured by using a suspended level Ubbelohde type viscometer having a flow time of 341 s for water at 35°. It was fitted in the (water) thermostatic bath in a reproducible position with metallic holder to ensure verticality. The viscometer was exhaustively cleaned and rinsed several times with experimental solutions. The viscosity coefficient of the solutions (0.05 M) were determined at 35 ± 0.05 and $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The corresponding densities, as required for the purpose, were measured by using a specific gravity bottle.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 records the mean cell constant, the concentrations of the solutions studied, D_{KCl} at 25° (noted from literature⁶), viscosity coefficients of aqueous tetraalkylammonium salts as well as the diffusion coefficients (D_{obs}) of the latter at 35 and 40°, computed by using equation (1). The standard deviation calculated for three diffusion and three viscosity runs under a given set of experimental conditions for various D and η values have been given in the parenthesis below the appropriate D and η .

With the increase of molecular weight of the solute, the diffusion and thermal strolling take place at a relatively low velocity, decreasing thereby the diffusion coefficient, probably due to the 'obstruction (hindering) effect'. The latter tends to be the function of the volume fraction as well as the shape and size of the solute⁴. The experimental results at each temperature are in agreement with this trend (Table 1).

A satisfactory agreement for nearly all the solutes between the observed ratios of D_{35}/D_{40} and the

ratio, η_{40}/η_{35} (308/313), as can be seen from the last two columns of Table 1, demonstrates the reliability of the given results in the light of the Stokes-Einstein relations, namely $D = kT/6\pi\eta r$, the terms involved having the usual significance.

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^{13}C Spectra as a Tool for Configurational Assignment of Oximes

S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN*, S. MUTHUSUBRAMANIAN**
and

N. ARUMUGAM

Department of Organic Chemistry, Madurai-Kamaraaj
University, Madurai-625 021

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IN the ^1H nmr spectra, the α -hydrogens *syn* to the hydroxyl got more deshielded than the α -hydrogens *anti* to it¹. On the otherhand, in the ^{13}C nmr spectra, the α -carbons which are *syn* to hydroxyl got more shielded when compared to the *anti* α -carbons². It is obvious that this correlation can be used only when both the isomeric oximes are available and not to those oximes which are characterised by the existence of only one of the isomeric oximes. To arrive at the configuration of the latter case of oximes, we have recently developed a method,³ wherein we compared the chemical shift values of the α -hydrogens of the oximes and those of the corresponding ketones. We successfully used the above method to fix the configurations of several cyclic ketoximes^{1,3-6}. In this paper, we report how the ^{13}C chemical shifts could be used as a tool to arrive at the configuration of the above mentioned type of oximes. This method will be useful when the ^1H nmr is helpless for these type of oximes.

It has been observed, in many cases, that while going from a ketone to oxime, the α -carbon *syn* to the hydroxyl are shielded to the extent of nearly

14.0 ppm while the α -carbons *anti* to the hydroxyl are shielded to the extent of less than 8.0 ppm. For example, considering the methyl ethyl ketone and its oximes, cyclohexanone and its oximes and 4-*t*-butylcyclohexanone and its oximes, it could be seen from Table 1 that the above statement is true. It is now proposed that this general pattern in the ^{13}C spectral studies could be used to assign the configuration of oximes where only one isomer is available.

TABLE 1— ^{13}C CHEMICAL SHIFT DATA OF METHYL ETHYL KETONE, CYCLOHEXANONE, 4-*t*-BUTYL-CYCLOHEXANONE AND THEIR OXIMES

Compd.	Chemical shift values of			
	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{CH}_2-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2^{\text{a}} \\ \quad \quad \\ 1 \quad 2 \quad 3 \quad 4 \end{array}$	27.50	206.25	35.20	17.00
$\begin{array}{c} \text{HO}-\text{N} \\ \parallel \\ \text{CH}_2-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2^{\text{b}} \\ \quad \quad \\ \text{N}-\text{CH} \\ \parallel \\ \text{CH}_2-\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2^{\text{b}} \end{array}$	13.00	158.70	29.00	11.00
	19.25	159.20	21.25	9.75
	Chemical shift value of α -carbon in			
	ketone	<i>syn</i> oxime	<i>anti</i> oxime	
Cyclohexanone and its oxime	41.90	24.40	32.00	
4- <i>t</i> -Butylcyclohexanone and oxime ^c	41.20	24.40	32.00	

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRefs. 10, 11.

We have employed this technique in some 2-aryl-cyclohexenone oximes (1a-c, Table 2) prepared by us⁷. In these cases, it could be readily seen that C-2 carbon gets shielded to the extent of 4 ppm or less, while the C-6 carbon gets shielded to the extent of 14 ppm, compared to the parent ketone (2) indicating that the C-6 carbon is *syn* to the hydroxyl group. Obviously, the hydroxyl group is *anti* to the C-2 substituent.

The ^{13}C nmr spectra were obtained at 90.56 MHz in a Bruker WM 460 spectrometer for approximately 0.5 M solutions in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard. A pulse angle of 37.5° (5 μs) and a repetition time of 3.72 s were used, collecting 32 K data points in the quadrature detection mode for a spectral width of 22 700 Hz at 20–21°. The multiplicity were identified by the usual methods under off-resonance conditions.

a; R = Phenyl
b; R = 4-Methylphenyl
c; R = 4-Isopropylphenyl

** Present Address: Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya Arts College, Coimbatore-641 020.